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Book Review : Aid, Development and Diplomacy: Need for an Aid Policy

Book By Muhammad Shamsul Huq And Chowdhury Rafiqul Abrar

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Abstract:

The book *Aid, Development and Diplomacy: Need for an Aid Policy* by Muhammad Shamsul Huq and Chowdhury Rafiqul Abrar addresses the critical need for an effective aid policy in Bangladesh, emphasizing the evolving role of aid in national development. The authors argue for a comprehensive approach that integrates economic growth with human development, underlining the importance of modifying Bangladesh's aid diplomacy to attract more substantial and beneficial aid. The book explores the evolution of foreign aid, Bangladesh's aid dependency, conditionalities imposed by donors, and case studies illustrating the challenges and successes of aid implementation. The authors also examine the necessity of a coherent diplomatic strategy to improve aid negotiation. While the book offers valuable insights, it suggests that a more participatory and rational approach to policymaking is crucial for achieving sustainable development. However, it also highlights the ongoing issues with bureaucratic inefficiencies and corruption that hamper aid utilization. The book ultimately calls for greater coordination in aid diplomacy and a shift towards policies that prioritize human development alongside economic growth.

Features of the Book

- **Title of Book:** Aid, Development and Diplomacy: Need for an Aid Policy
- **Authors:** Muhammad Shamsul Huq And Chowdhury Rafiqul Abrar
- **Publisher:** The University Press Limited, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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- **Cover:** Paperback

About the Author

Professor Muhammad Shamsul Huq was an eminent educationist, Vice Chancellor of the University of Rajshahi (1965-69) and the University of Dhaka (1975-76). He served as the Central Minister of Education and Scientific and Technological Research during 1969-71. As the President's Adviser on Foreign affairs during 1977-78 and Foreign Minister during 1978-82, he played a key role in the shaping of Bangladesh's foreign policy.

Prof. Huq was a scholar-in residence at the Institute of Advanced Projects, East-West Centre, Hawaii, and a Senior Fellow at the Woodrow Wilson International Centre for Scholars. He was the President of the Foundation for Research on Educational Planning and Development (FREPD), Dhaka.

He has authored a number of books including Education Manpower and Development in South and Southeast Asia (Praeger Publisher Inc. 1975), International Politics: A Third World Perspective (Sterling, 1987) and Bangladesh in International Politics: The Dilemmas of the Weak States (Sterling and The University Press Limited, 1993). Prof. Huq has also contributed to Encyclopaedia Britannica and the German Encyclopaedia.

Chowdhury Rafiqul Abrar studied at the Universities of Dhaka, Sussex and Griffith, Australia. His articles were included in volumes published by Westview Press, Blackwell, Earth scan and Macmillan, India. Dr. Abrar teaches International Relations at the University of Dhaka.

1.0 Introduction

There has been a change regarding the perception of development which has attained a wider meaning over the last few decades. True and actual development takes place when economic growth as well as human development is achieved simultaneously. In this book, the authors have emphasized the changed focus of development and argued cogently that the Government of Bangladesh (GOB) should keep this change in mind when designing an effective aid policy to attract more aid for development. They have cited examples showing that today, the attitude of major donors, particularly the World Bank, has changed in the light of this transformed concept of development. Thus, it is imperative for the GOB to modify its aid policy-making process and diplomacy so that it can negotiate more efficiently with major donors for aid on justified terms and conditions and operate the grant for comprehensive development.

The growing criticism of the role and performance of foreign aid in Bangladesh deserves a thorough and objective evaluation of the policy pursued by Bangladesh in attracting and using external aid and its impact on national development.

2.0 Chapter wise Subject Matter

Chapter 01: Aid, Development and Diplomacy: Concept and Context

The authors started this chapter with the evolution of aid regime. The linkage between aid and development has been stated clearly. The numerous form of external aids and their sources are described extensively. Foreign aid has clearly emerged as a critical factor in diplomacy used by the donor and recipient countries in promoting through mutually acceptable programmes their national objectives, goals and values. Economic development is responsible for only a part of quality of life and the rest of the part of the life is closely associated with human and social development.

The authors have shifted the focus of the concept of the development very clearly. The human factor is the key issue to the sustainable development with external aid that plays a critical role in acceleration the pace of development. Human development has become a critical aspect of development. Economic growth and development policies should also be sensitive to environmental concerns. National development, which is of utmost priority, should be based on this comprehensive concept of development. Poverty reduction, employment generation,

education, health, etc., which are an integral part of comprehensive development, assume importance in this regard. Aid diplomacy should be used by the GOB to meet these needs.

Chapter 02: Bangladesh's Aid Scenario

The second chapter focuses on Bangladesh's aid scenario and its changes. Foreign aid has become an important tool for economic development of Bangladesh. During the twenty six years (1971-1995) of its existence Bangladesh has received \$29 billion of external aid. The obvious dependence of Bangladesh's economy on external assistance has been generally explained by a number of economists in terms of two gaps model. The country's inability to generate enough savings for investment on one hand, and earn adequate foreign exchange to pay for imports, on other, has necessitated continued flow of foreign aid. The authors has supported this theory.

Foreign aid to Bangladesh has officially been categorized under three main heads, Project Aid, Commodity Aid and Food Aid. Project Aid constituted half of the \$29.04bln of foreign assistance that Bangladesh received so far. Projects under the Annual Development Plan (ADP) are generally financed under Project Aid. Commodity Aid is the type of aid that is spent for the procurement of intermediate inputs and raw materials. Since 1972 Commodity Aid constituted 31.51% of the total aid volume to Bangladesh. Food Aid constituted 18.32% of the total aid received. The authors stated and described this matter by incorporating appropriate table.

There has been a difference between aid commitment and disbursement figures. Although till 1995 total foreign aid committed to Bangladesh amounted \$35.13bln the amount actually disbursed stood at \$29.01bln. The percentage of disbursement of food, commodity and project aid to commitment was 98.51, 96.62, and 71.79 respectively.

The allocation of foreign aid (project aid) to different sector has been discussed in this chapter. It is seen that Power received the largest allocation \$2788.9 (19.14%), followed by transport and communication \$2627.8 (18.07%). Other infrastructural development projects (water, flood control, housing and cyclone shelters) constitute the third largest sector accounting for \$2125.8 (14.59%). Agriculture and rural development accounted for 12.35% of foreign aid allocation. It is important to note that human development sectors (health, education etc.) accounted for only 12.57% of the total resources mobilized. There is a general bias towards large scale projects on one hand, and also towards projects which demand more external inputs, on the other.

The authors here highlighted different sources, types of aid and the components of the grant and loans very clearly.

In the context of Bangladesh donors feel that it is extremely difficult to reach the poor through the existing government machinery. This is because of corruption, misappropriation of funds, overlapping of power of various government bodies, bureaucratic red-tapism etc. In this context, donors feel channeling funds through NGOs, is justifiable because NGOs (a) are geared specifically to the needs of the poor, (b) operate at a low cost, (c) can ensure beneficiary participation, (d) are relatively free from bureaucratic hierarchy, and (e) are flexible and innovative in their approach. Donors also consistently influence the government to establish favorable public policy framework for the NGOs.

Chapter 03: Conditionalities and Aid Utilization

The differing perceptions of the GOB and donors in respect of conditionalities and aid utilisation is the theme of the third chapter, reflecting the problems associated with foreign aid in LDCs such as Bangladesh.

Normally conditionalities are imposed multilaterally, they come not as requests but as directives. Human rights, environment and transparency are some of the relatively newer elements in conditionality. With respect to conditionality there have been mixed responses. Conditionalities may be imposed at different levels project, sectoral or macro-economic. For projects like power plant it deals with where it will be located, who will be implementing them, what will be the work schedule and how the product will be sold, who will manage the facility, supply of inputs, operation and maintenance, pricing delivery of services flowing from the project etc. For sectoral issues like power sector it involves input pricing, sector management (public and private), distribution system (whether there will be monopoly or competition), control of decisions etc. For macro-economic issues money supply, inflation, trade pattern, exchange rate, budget etc. are important considerations.

Under the scheme the *World Bank* and the *Asian Development Bank (ADB)* disbursed cash money in exchange of fulfilment of some tough conditions to reform the financial, energy, agriculture, public resource management, jute and other industries sector.

Individual donors place their conditions at bilateral meetings. Major donors like *Japan* and *Germany* are disposed towards a sound macro-economic management. There are some conditionalities imposed by the donors which are conducive to national interest.

Some donors' demand for consultation with the people, by holding workshops and discussions to assess feasibility of projects, has had positive results in ensuring transparency and accountability. "The setting of any conditionality on an investment, represents prudent housekeeping ultimately to protect the interests of the public in the aid recipient county and the taxpayer of the donor country"- author cited from the then British High Commissioner, 1995.

Performance and aid utilization capacity are major justifications for reduction of aid. Major donors share the view that Bangladesh does have a problem of implementation capacity which has led to the slow utilization of aid on offer. In Japanese perception, compared to east and Southeast Asian countries the aid utilization problem is more acute in Bangladesh. Bureaucratic inefficiency, red-tapism and service un-oriented administration are the major area concern.

The authors described the view of different donors regarding imposing numerous conditionalities to the recipient countries. Authors also identified different problems and impediments to the project implementation like delay in disbursement, reluctance of donors to flexibility in budgeting, wrong choice of project, legal framework etc.

The remedial measures suggested this chapter to improve aid utilization capacity are that (i) GoB should seek improvements in public management and civil service reform, (ii) the people of Bangladesh should develop the norms, values and institutions of civil society which will lead to greater responsiveness on behalf of Ministers and civil servants to the priority needs of the people.

Chapter 04: Case Studies

Project aid utilization had indeed been the bone of contention between the GOB and the donors. The authors do well in treating it specially by analyzing two projects—one successfully implemented and the other a failure—in the fourth chapter. The reasons for success and failure have been well documented.

These two case studies, representing two major development projects, stand out in contrast. The Rural Roads and Markets Improvement & Maintenance Project -1 (RRMIMP1) was a success story. The factors contributing to its success were pre-eminently professional competence in project designing, speedy processing and approval of the project proposal, timely disbursement of aid fund, delegation of decision-making authority to the implementing agency, spirit of partnership between the expatriate consultants and their local counterparts,

flexibility in implementation to suit ground realities, adequate training of personnel and their uninterrupted continuity on the job, and above all work ethos and leadership

In other case, namely the Second Gas Development Project (SGDP), the progress in implementation was stymied and the period of implementation prolonged by three and a half years. The causes were principally inordinate delay in project approval, delay in disbursement of funds by the donors, centralized and multi-tier decision making process, lack of coordination between the donor co-financing agencies and the GoB, transfer of key personnel during the project life and under-utilization of trained personnel.

Chapter 05: Aid and its Impact on Development

The fifth chapter analyses the reasons for Bangladesh lagging behind in various aspects of development. It suggests that this issue be addressed by its ensuring that its policy-making is more participatory, involving the poor whose lives are affected, so that they may benefit from the recent economic changes brought about by the forces of globalization. Development would then be extended to a wider section of the population.

Many of the donors now acknowledge that people are at the centre of development both as a means and an end and that development is pre-eminently a human process. The objectives of any development plan will be productive employment, achievement of food self-sufficiency, human resources development, development of infrastructure, curbing population growth, provision of social amenities, strengthening of technological base, protection of environment, closing the gender gap and establishment of better social justice through a more equitable distribution of income.

The authors stated that gender gaps in Bangladesh continue to exist and even expand adversely affecting the situation of women in poverty and their development. One way to achieve poverty eradication is through specialized micro credit institutions targeting the poor families besides providing an access to financial resources. Eradication of poverty is a complex and formidable problem and clearly warrants a concerted action programme to be implemented both globally and nationally.

Chapter 06: Aid and Diplomacy: The Need for an Aid Policy

The sixth chapter argues that diplomacy in Bangladesh has remained fragmented and thereby failed to project the country's image to negotiate with major donors for aid on justified terms. To achieve this purpose, diplomacy needs to be more coherent and well-coordinated.

The authors analyzes that the inherent weakness of a nation is a disadvantage in diplomatic negotiations. This disadvantage is compounded by fragmented economic diplomacy arising from internal divisiveness, lack of coordination, inter-ministerial rivalry, lack of adequate professional skill and allegedly widespread corruption within the government. These factors largely account for unfavorable terms of aid and loan (including FDI). Aid policy is an integral part of economic policy

3.0 Critical Analysis

The book, however, has not addressed other issues more seriously. The relation between aid and development and aid and liberalization needed to be covered at greater depth. Less developed countries, such as Bangladesh, will always receive aid to meet its development requirements. The authors should have placed this issue in a comparative perspective. A comparison of the Bangladesh experience with that of other LDCs may have revealed something that is unique to Bangladesh, impeding its development process through foreign aid. Has foreign aid contributed to the development process of other LDCs or even some developed countries? In this age of liberalization, what is the role of aid? Such questions need to be explored. It is true that greater and faster economic reforms have been an essential conditionality for grants in aid by the developed countries in the 1990s. However, in many cases there has been less aid flow, notwithstanding reforms. This is true in the case of Bangladesh. There is also a serious need to evaluate whether the blame for less aid flow to Bangladesh is to be attributed to the GOB or the donors. Despite criticisms about project implementation, some of the major donors have given Bangladesh project grants in the 1990s. It is apparent that the donors would not be so tough with an LDC such as Bangladesh, as to impose conditionalities that are impossible to fulfil.

Finally, it is true that policy-making has to be more participatory for a more rational aid policy. However, a crucial question is whether the vested interests in society and the bureaucracy will allow this to take place. The authors should have highlighted some GOB initiatives, if any, in this regard. Further, discussion on the future relevance of foreign aid would have been pertinent, particularly as foreign direct investment has emerged as a mode of capital flow into the LDCs.

4.0 Conclusion

The core message in Aid, Development and Diplomacy: Need for an Aid Policy is that development of a country should be sustainable and aid diplomacy should be coherent and well-coordinated to attain this. It is necessary to go through this book by related policy maker for getting vivid idea about the relation between development, aid and economic diplomacy.